

Review

Analyzing the core health system challenges associated with health workforce, financing and governance in achieving universal health coverage in Bangladesh

Faojia Sultana^{1*}

¹Institute of Health Economics, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract: Achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC) in a country refers to the state of having equitable access to essential healthcare services by their entire population without them suffering any financial adversities associated with the healthcare cost. Bangladesh has not yet been successful in establishing UHC due to numerous health system weaknesses. The aim of this review was to explore the challenges associated with three key health system building blocks (i.e., health workforce, healthcare financing, and health sector governance), and demonstrate how they were hindering Bangladesh's progress towards achieving UHC. As the theoretical framework, the health systems framework by WHO was used here in conjunction with the evidence generated by Reich et al. (2016) on how certain countries have successfully adopted and implemented UHC. Accordingly, an extensive literature search was conducted on PubMed, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and relevant organizational websites. Findings from this review identified shortage, skill-mix imbalance, and inequitable geographical distribution as the most critical health workforce challenges in Bangladesh. Secondly, low health budget, absence of national health insurance, and high out-of-pocket expenditure were evident as some crucial health financing barriers. Finally, the lack of a strong regulatory framework and well-defined chain of accountability coupled with their highly centralized healthcare system created some grave governance issues in health sector of Bangladesh. Their cumulative impact is weakening the health system and deterring the country's attainment of UHC.

Keywords: Universal Health Coverage, Health System, Health Workforce, Healthcare Financing, Health Sector Governance, Bangladesh

*Corresponding Author: Faojia Sultana

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1. Introduction

Universal Health Coverage (UHC) has long been a priority global health agenda, and is a crucial target (target 3.8) of the United Nations' 2015 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). UHC means ensuring access to essential and quality

healthcare services (promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative) to all citizens at an affordable cost without risking financial hardship.¹ Nevertheless, many low-and middle-income countries (LMICs) are struggling to redesign and strengthen their health system to fulfill the goals of UHC; and the situation in Bangladesh has not been an exception. Despite being a low-income country, Bangladesh has made some remarkable progress in the health sector in recent decades. They have achieved significant headway in lowering their infant and maternal mortality rates,² while their average life expectancy has risen to 68.3 years.³ This achievement, however, was unequal across various socioeconomic and geographic groups of population within the country. Based on the absolute and relative indices of inequity, it has been observed that vulnerable population groups such as the rural population and the urban slum-dwellers of the country have suffered from a disproportionate experience during this apparent period of health sector accomplishments in Bangladesh.⁴ Such a scenario has been termed as the 'Bangladesh Paradox' by Chowdhury et al. which has been used to describe a situation in which the noteworthy improvement in some of the indicators of health in the country has co-existed with issues such as the growing disparities between the rich and poor sections of the population, the evident inequity in the distribution of healthcare across the country, and the constant underutilization of some essential health services.⁵ Furthermore, the health system of Bangladesh is having to cope with the pressure of their concurrent demographic and epidemiologic transition which has given rise to a growing burden of noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) along with a notable increase in the number of the elderly population in the country.⁶ However, to attain the objectives of UHC in a country, it is paramount to have a strong and effective health system that can deal with the changing dynamics of the healthcare needs of every one of its citizens irrespective of their socio-demographic strata. Accordingly, the World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the importance of maintaining a proper balance between the six building blocks of the health systems framework to build and sustain a healthcare delivery system capable of achieving UHC in a country (Figure-1).⁷

Figure 1: World Health Organization (WHO) health systems framework ⁷

Accordingly, the WHO health systems framework has been used as the theoretical framework for this review. In addition, the evidence from Reich et al. (2016) was used as the guiding principles to isolate the key building blocks (out of the six WHO building blocks) which have been evident to be significantly hindering a country’s progress in achieving UHC.⁸ Based on the global experiences of adopting and implementing UHC, Reich et al. have reported that to build a solid foundation for the achievement of UHC in a country, it is crucial to strengthen three key building blocks from the WHO health systems framework which are healthcare financing, health workforce/ human resources for health (HRH), and governance/ leadership. Healthcare financing and human resources denote the two primary and most vital inputs

for any health system. In addition, to shape any policy decisions regarding the health system and/or UHC, and to better handle the political trade-offs, conflicts, and negotiation in a country, having good governance and leadership in their entire system is obligatory.^{7,8}

Therefore, the objective of this paper is to analyze the barriers associated with these three key building blocks of the WHO health systems framework and to establish their linkages with the advancement of UHC in Bangladesh. The definitive goal is to identify the current pitfalls in the health workforce, healthcare financing, and health sector governance building blocks of the WHO framework to demonstrate how they are hindering the development of an equitable, efficient and sustainable health system necessary for attaining UHC in Bangladesh.

2. Methodology

An extensive literature review was conducted using a systematic approach to gather relevant data on the health system of Bangladesh and UHC for our analysis. As the theoretical framework for this analysis, the health systems framework by WHO (Figure 1) was used in conjunction with the evidence generated by Reich et al. (2016) which emphasized the significance of three particular health system building blocks (i.e., health workforce, healthcare financing, and health sector governance) from the WHO framework on the successful adoption and implementation of UHC in a country (Figure-2).⁸

Figure 2: Three key health system components/building blocks essential for moving towards UHC in a country ⁸

[Note: Adopted from Reich et al. (2016)]

To identify relevant published and grey literature regarding UHC in Bangladesh, a comprehensive search was conducted on PubMed, Web of Science, Google Scholar, Google, WHO, and World Bank research portals, and web pages of the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) of Bangladesh. The combinations of the following keywords and synonyms in conjunction with the controlled vocabulary of the database were used: 'universal health coverage', 'UHC', 'health system', 'healthcare system', 'health Workforce', 'human resources for health', 'healthcare Professionals', 'healthcare providers', 'health service', 'health service coverage', 'health financing', 'healthcare financing', 'financial protection', 'governance', 'challenges', 'barriers', 'assessment', 'Bangladesh'. These keywords were applied in conjunction with Boolean operators (AND, OR) as required. When searching via Google Scholar, the search was fixed by date (after 1971) and relevance (proximity to the terms). 'Reference mining' was done by searching the bibliographies of the included articles for additional relevant publications. All English literature published after 1971 (i.e., the year Bangladesh gained their independence), relevant to Bangladesh health sector, and with regards to UHC and health systems were included for analysis.

The search of the database and websites was applied on September 10, 2021, which yielded 1086 records initially. After the preliminary screening, 89 sources were selected, and the rest were removed due to record duplication and unavailability of full texts. Then, 58 full-text articles were chosen based on the abstract. From those, another 21 sources were excluded due to imperfectly matching the scope of this review, and containing outdated and controversial findings. Finally, 37 journal articles, grey literature and ministry documents were included in the final analysis for this review (Figure 3).

Figure 3: PRISMA flow diagram of literature search
 (PRISMA=Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)

The content of the selected literature was thoroughly reviewed and analyzed to identify the elements that produced challenges and bottlenecks for the health system of Bangladesh and hindered their progress towards UHC. To ensure representation and legitimation of the review, multiple and varied sources of materials such as journal publications, reports, bulletins, documents, policy briefs etc. were collected which helped with the between-source data triangulation and initiation. Additionally, within-study and between studies literature analyses were conducted to verify and cross-check the validity of the retrieved information.⁹

3. Result

3.1| Brief overview of Bangladesh and their health system

Bangladesh is a small South-Asian country with a population of 165 million within an area of 147, 570 square kilometers.¹⁰ The country has relatively low levels of health and educational status and continually struggles with critical challenges such as poverty, corruption, overpopulation, and vulnerability to climate change.⁵

Bangladesh has a pluralistic health system, comprised of four key actors: 1) Government or public sector, 2) Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), 3) Private sector and 4) Donor agencies ¹¹. Government or public sector plays a

key role in the provision and management of healthcare in the country. In terms of administrative and policy-making power, the health system of the country is highly centralized.¹² The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) is not only in charge of planning and formulating national health policies, but also provision and monitoring of health services fall under their jurisdiction.¹³ MoHFW delivers healthcare through various levels of facilities organized under a three-tiered (primary, secondary, and tertiary) network (Figure-3).¹¹ However, the lack of referral and coordination mechanisms between these three tiers of facilities often results in overburdening of upper-level facilities. Ministry of Local Government, Rural Development and Cooperatives (MoLGRDC) provide urban primary healthcare through contracting services from private providers/NGOs (Figure-4).¹² Nevertheless, the absence of a structured primary care delivery system in urban areas makes the urbanites dependent on secondary and tertiary level public and private healthcare facilities. There is also an extensive network of private healthcare providers and facilities in Bangladesh. However, the price and quality of their services have been a matter of persistent concern.¹⁴ The other two actors in Bangladesh health sector are the NGOs and the donors, both of whom play a significant role in shaping the health system.¹⁵

Figure 4: Organization and structure of the healthcare delivery system in Bangladesh

Bangladesh gained their independence as a country in 1971; but, their first National Health Policy (NHP) was approved by the Parliament in 2000. Therefore, all health-related planning and programming during this period were guided by the national 'Five-Year' plans, the achievements and failures of which molded the development and structure of the country's health sector to a great extent (Figure 5).¹²

Figure 5: Summary of the key achievements and failures of the first four national 'Five-Year Plans' implemented in the health sector of Bangladesh ^{12, 24}

During the late 1990s, several health sector reforms were made by the government resulting in the formulation of the National Health Policy (NHP) and the sector-wide Health, Population, and Nutrition (HPN) programs as a substitute for the 'Five-Year' plans.¹² In 2012, the national 'Health Care Financing Strategy' (HCFS) of Bangladesh was developed to help further the objectives of UHC.¹⁶ But, to this date the attainment of UHC has not been successful in the county.

3.2| Key barriers in attaining UHC in Bangladesh

3.2.1| Health workforce challenges

A well-functioning health system relies heavily on its human resources. A higher density of healthcare workers has been found to be associated with a reducing maternal, infant, and under-five mortality rates based on the WHO data.¹⁷ However, Bangladesh's health system has long been plagued by a critical shortage of human resources. Furthermore, other health workforce challenges such as an imbalanced mix of HRH (particularly a lower number of nurses),

geographical inequity in HRH distribution, unsatisfactory wages, and out-of-country migration of doctors have exacerbated Bangladesh's HRH challenges which in turn have been affecting the quality of healthcare services in the country.^{6, 18}

According to WHO, a minimum of 23 HCPs per 10,000 people are required to provide at least adequate maternal healthcare coverage in a country.¹⁹ In another report, ILO further suggested that this WHO threshold of required HCPs should be increased to 41 per 10,000 population. Because to progress the UHC agenda of the SDGs, factors such as population growth, aging, and the increasing burden of NCDs need to be included in the calculation of the HCP requirement.²⁰ Nevertheless, the 2017 global monitoring report for tracking UHC stated that Bangladesh only had 0.4 physicians per 1000 populations and 1.7 surgeons per 100,000 people.¹ Inadequate government spending in the health sector and faulty provider payment mechanism have been identified as two key reasons behind such shortage of HCPs in the country. Additionally, the complex civil service recruitment process of HCPs and failure to fill up and retain all of the government-sanctioned posts have been found to pose additional challenges as evident by the fact that one-fifth of the government-sanctioned posts for the HCPs remain vacant each year. Individually, the vacancy rates for physicians, nurses, and medical technicians are estimated to be 27%, 22%, and 21%, respectively.⁶

Geographical maldistribution issues of HCPs have also been reported across the country which was evident by the shortage of qualified HCPs in their remote and rural areas.²¹ A higher vacancy rate was also experienced in the public healthcare facilities located in rural areas (26%).²² Even though more than 70% of Bangladesh's population still lives in rural areas, the overall doctor-to-population ratio in rural areas was determined to be 1:15,000 which was ten times worse than it was in the urban regions of the country.^{23, 24} This propensity of HCPs to work in urban areas has been attributed to certain 'push and pull' factors. Lack of proper infrastructure and equipment, weak administrative support, unsafe work environment (especially for female providers), and limited in-service training opportunities in rural facilities along with the absence of structured incentive mechanisms have been identified as some key 'push' factors. On another hand, the presence of major teaching and training hospitals, better private practice opportunities (as the wealthier quintile of the population lives in urban areas), better work environment and living standards act as the 'pull' factors for the HCPs for wanting to work in urban regions rather than the rural areas.⁶ Similar 'pull' factors from the developed countries also contribute to the out-country migration ('brain drain') of many skilled HCPs from Bangladesh each year. For instance, 28% of medical doctors who graduated in 1985, migrated to other countries in the subsequent years.²²

In addition, there has been a chronic skill-mix imbalance problem in the health workforce of Bangladesh. The ratio between doctors, nurses, and technicians in the country were found to be 1 to 0.4 to 0.24, which runs contrary to the 1 to 3 to 5 ratio suggested by the WHO.¹² Further evidence has also shown a significant association between the skill-mix imbalance within the health workforce and the poorer health outcomes among the population in the country.²⁵ For instance, when a comparison was made between the health outcomes between two administrative divisions of Bangladesh, it was evident that the divisional city with an equal ratio of doctors and nurses did better on several health indicators compared to the division which had a lower nurse to doctor ratio.²¹

Owing to such challenges and concerns within the public sector health workforce of Bangladesh, opportunities have arisen for the healthcare providers in the private sector (both formal and informal) to extend their network of healthcare practice throughout the country.²¹ There is a widespread network of informal healthcare providers such as traditional healers, village doctors, drugstore salesmen, traditional birth attendants (TBAs) etc. in the country, and the dominance of such practitioners is particularly strong in the rural areas. Accordingly, the presence of 64.2 traditional healers and 33.2 TBAs compared to only 7.7 formally qualified doctors, dentists, and nurses per 10,000 people is a testament to their large network, and acceptance among the general people (*Figure 6*).²⁶

Figure 6: Density of healthcare providers (formal and informal) per 10,000 population in Bangladesh ²⁶

According to data from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics from 2016, approximately 23% of sick people in the country sought care from physicians working in the private sector, 33% went to pharmacists or compounders, and only about 15% visited recognized public sector facilities.²⁷ A gross inequity in the geographical distribution of formally qualified versus semi/unqualified HCPs has thus developed in Bangladesh (Figure 7), resulting in the predominance of informal providers in rural areas and formally qualified professionals in urban regions.²¹ However, in most cases, these private sector informal HCPs were found to have a subpar level of knowledge and skills owing to their lack of professional training.²⁸ Therefore, the quality of healthcare provided by them has often been considered below average and concerning in nature by scholars and experts in the health sector.²⁹

Figure 7: Urban and rural distribution(%) of healthcare providers (formal and informal) in Bangladesh ²⁶

3.2.1| Healthcare financing barriers

Financial risk protection is a critical component of UHC which is why establishing an effective health financing mechanism is crucial to achieve UHC in a country.³⁰ In terms of health financing in Bangladesh, the government and the households are primarily responsible for the payment of healthcare goods and services.³¹ However, according to the 2012 national health expenditure data, only 7.7% of the total government budget was being spent on the health sector, which was way below the global average of 12%. It was also fairly inadequate compared to the ideal budget required for the implementation UHC (*Table-1*).³²

Table 1: Public Expenditure Requirement for UHC in Bangladesh (in BDT*)

Indicators	2009/10	2014/15	2019/20	2024/25
Total public health expenditure ideally required for UHC (in million BDT)	274,173	308,763	340,899	376,381
Estimated healthcare budget with 65% growth rate (in million BDT)	68,320	91,427	122,350	163,732
Deficit to achieve UHC (in million BDT)	205,853	217,335	218,549	212, 648
Amount of budget if the government provides 50% of the ideally required budget for UHC (in million BDT)	137,086	154,382	170,450	188,190
Amount of budget if the government provides 40% of the ideally required budget for UHC (in million BDT)	109,669	123,505	136,360	150,552
Amount of budget if the government provides 25% of the ideally required budget for UHC (in million BDT)	68,543	77,190	85,224	94,095

(*BDT= Bangladeshi Taka)

[Note: Adapted from Chowdhury, A., et al. (2012)³²]

The 2014 UHC assessment report revealed that out of the 3.4% of GDP that was spent on health in Bangladesh, only 1.1% was contributed by the government and the rest was financed by the private sector.³³ According to the global health expenditure database of WHO, around 74% of the country's annual health financing came from private funds, more specifically from 'out-of-pocket expenditure' (OOPE) by the people, whereas the government contribution was about 17%.³⁴ This has made the Bangladesh health system highly regressive in nature. Moreover, there is no national health insurance scheme in the country which could have allowed for cross-subsidization and risk pooling for their vulnerable and disadvantaged people. Although there are some private pre-payment insurances in place by private firms and NGOs, but the role of these third-party payment mechanisms has been quite insignificant (0.2% only). Apart from them, the other major contributor to Bangladesh health sector budget has been the international donors (6.5%). Therefore, if we roughly divide the health expenditure between the public and private sectors, then private financing makes up for more than two-thirds of the total health expenditure in Bangladesh (*Figure 8*).³⁴

Figure 8: Sources of healthcare financing in Bangladesh ³⁴

There has also been gross inequity in the budgetary allocation in the health sector. Inputs and demands from the local bodies in the health sector were not reflected in the ultimate allocative decisions as they were being made centrally by the Ministry based on the previous year's expenditure; available funding; and the policy agenda of the ruling party rather than the actual local need. With an already low government health budget, such impractical and insufficient allocation forced many households to pay out of their own pocket for healthcare. The poor reportedly suffered more from this allocative inefficiency. Accordingly, the MoHFW expenditure data has revealed that the richest quintile of the country received more benefits from the government healthcare allocation (27%) compared to the poorest quintile (21%).²⁴

Furthermore, the three-tiered public healthcare delivery system of Bangladesh was built to provide care for a nominal fee along with the provision of essential medicines free of cost.³⁵ But due to the lack of adequate government financing, the majority of these public facilities were found to be ill-equipped to provide better service coverage and quality of care.²⁴ For 160 million people in the country, there were only 37,837 inpatient care beds present in all of the 536 public hospitals.¹² Lack of essential commodities like drugs and medical supplies at these facilities forced the patients to buy them from private pharmacies at a higher price. The cost of purchasing medicine, therefore, contributed to about 69% of the total OOPE in the country.³¹ Shortages of ambulances in public facilities were reported as well. Moreover, about 65% of the ambulances present in public facilities were often found to be in a 'non-functional' state, requiring the patients to pay for their own transportation costs to hospitals.³⁶ Based on the 2008 ILO/KFW study data, the BHW report 2011 stated that approximately 80% of respondents had to make some sort of OOPE (formal or informal) to receive healthcare from these 'free' hospitals.³² Also, 20% of government service users made unofficial payments directly to the service workers.²⁸ This 'user-fee' dependent health financing system has put the poor households at greater financial risk and often exposed them to catastrophic 'health shocks' resulting from medical expenditures.³⁷ The World Bank report 2008 stated that such 'health shocks' were the most significant shocks that occurred to Bangladeshi people

accounting for about 22% of all financial shocks suffered by them. In fact, among the countries in the Asia Pacific region, Bangladesh has the highest incidence of catastrophic health expenditures (CHE).³⁸ Jahangir et. al found that the incidences of CHE were higher in the rural (16.3%) population compared to the urban (8.6) and were concentrated more in the households with lower socioeconomic status. They also reported that due to OOP spending on healthcare, 3.5% of the total Bangladeshi population fell into poverty each year leading to the economic impoverishment of around 5 million people annually.¹⁵ According to another estimate, 7% of a household's OOP has cost the Bangladeshi people more than 25% of their monthly non-food expenses.³³ Now with the emerging double-burden of disease and the growing number of elderly populations in the country, incidences of health shocks are likely to increase at a higher rate in Bangladesh which will further deter their progress towards UHC.

To generate momentum toward the UHC initiatives, Bangladesh approved its first 'Health Care Financing Strategy' (HCFS) in 2012, which outlined a roadmap to achieve UHC by 2032. The initial proposal of the HCFS was to establish a Health Protection Fund that would include a contributory regime for formal sector workers and a non-contributory health program (Shasthyo Suroksha Karmasuchi'/SSK) for households below the poverty line.¹⁶ However, it has been nine years since the HCFS has been officially in motion, and the progress on the proposed plans has not been significant to this date.

So far the non-contributory regime of SSK has only been piloted on full-scale in three Upazilas (sub-district areas) of Bangladesh, and no concrete pre-payment model incorporating all the essential outpatient and inpatient healthcare needs of the targeted patient groups has yet been finalized.³⁹ Concerns regarding the sustainability of the proposed scheme for the informal sectors have also been raised due to its voluntary nature.⁶ However, these issues have not yet been clearly addressed by the authorities responsible for the implementation of the strategy. Moreover, considering the negative impact suffered by the health system of Bangladesh as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic, the likelihood of attaining the targets of HCFS by the projected timeline is getting increasingly slimmer.

3.2.3| Weak health sector governance

Good governance in the health system acts as a cornerstone for the movement towards UHC and has a direct effect on the health outcome of a country.⁴⁰ USAID defined governance as *'the ability of government to develop an efficient, effective, and accountable public management process that is open to participation and that strengthens rather than weakens a democratic system of government'*.⁴¹

In Bangladesh, the task of health sector governance is accredited to the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW). Being a highly centralized health system, the MoHFW almost autonomously has been in charge of both health policy making, and the provision of health services in the country. However, this has often acted as a barrier towards achieving transparency and accountability within the health system, thus weakening the process of governance.¹² Interaction between three sets of actors are key in maintaining health sector governance, namely a) Beneficiaries/service users, b) Political and government decision-makers, and c) Health service providers (*Figure 9*).⁴¹ But in reality, policy processes in Bangladesh have been dominated by the politicians and bureaucrats followed by the healthcare providers, and there has been no significant mechanism to involve the general population in the policy-making process, especially the poor and marginalized groups (*Figure 10*). Policy decisions taken in their health sector have often been influenced by the agenda of the political party in power, rather than the actual needs of the general population of the country.⁴²

Figure 9: Interaction between the three actors of health sector governance

Figure 10: Hierarchy between the three actors of health sector governance in Bangladesh

There has been a lack of strong administrative framework, institutions, and regulations for the management of physical and human resources, addressing patient needs and grievances, and for preventing malpractice and corruption within the health sector of the country. For example, statutory bodies such as Bangladesh Medical and Dental Council (BMDC), Bangladesh Nursing Council (BNC), State Medical Faculty, and Bangladesh Pharmacy Council (BPC) have been in place to ensure the development of a qualified health workforce and to regulate the ethical standards of practice in healthcare services. But in reality, the absence of clearly defined organizational capacities, political instability, and lack of culpability acted as some major obstacles in their way of functioning properly.⁴² Lack of distinct laws regarding the dual practice of public healthcare providers, and the absence of performance assessment mechanism for the renewal of their BMDC registration is also indicative of an ill-defined chain of accountability and monitoring within the system.¹² There has been no organized framework to address genuine patient grievances in the healthcare facilities of the country in a user-friendly way which has resulted in increased corruption and malpractices in the facilities, and worsened the sufferings of the patients.⁴² Lack of strict regulation has also resulted in the growing number of substandard private medical colleges, and the mushrooming of unregistered and unqualified informal sector healthcare providers all over the country.²⁶ Owing to the lack of strict monitoring and regulation by the Government, profit-oriented pharmaceutical market practices and unhealthy competition between the drug companies have correspondingly increased over the years as well. The local market has thus been swamped with poor-quality, expired, and counterfeit drugs. There are around 70,000 unlicensed and unregulated drugstores in Bangladesh selling drugs without prescriptions, and contributing to the irrational use of sensitive drugs in the country.⁴³

Evidence also suggests that people in the country have constantly suffered from limited access to healthcare services in public facilities because of factors such as absenteeism of healthcare professionals in rural facilities, charging of unofficial fees for healthcare, limited access to essential medications and supplies, distance cost, and social exclusion.⁴⁴ Ahmed et. al stated that according to Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) data, 44.1% of the households seeking health care were somehow victimized by corrupted practices either in the form of informal payments (bribes) for supposedly free services or, through the illegal sale of public hospital medicines outside by the employees.¹² These problems are a direct demonstration of an unaccountable, weak and non-transparent health sector governance which has been acting as a major barrier towards achieving a sustainable health system as well as UHC in Bangladesh.⁴²

4. Discussion

A comparative analysis of several countries has revealed that the combination of three prime elements is necessary to build a proper health system, which is, a) good governance and political commitment to support UHC; b) ideal health financing methods to support the coverage; and c) adoption of necessary regulation to resolve the shortage of human resources for health.⁸ Looking into the health system of Bangladesh, it is clear that there have been inadequacies in all of these three elements in their system.

Firstly, weak governance and stewardship have been impeding the efficiency and effectiveness of the Bangladesh health sector for decades now. There has been a constant absence of carefully crafted policy decisions and firm political will on the government's part which is essential for the betterment of the health system. Both adopting and implementing the desired UHC targets require political bartering and negotiation between different groups of stakeholders.⁴⁰ But there has been an apparent lack of strong leadership and commitment at the authoritative level of Bangladesh, which can be attributed as a root cause preventing a socio-political reform necessary to achieve UHC. The successful establishment of UHC by Thailand even after suffering through the Asian Financial crisis can be a valuable lesson for Bangladesh regarding strong governance. They have proven that economic stability is not an absolute necessity for expanding health coverage, rather strong political commitment and strategic management of stakeholder pressures can provide a solid foundation for expanding national healthcare coverage.⁴⁵ Furthermore, the planning, regulation, and monitoring capacity of MOHFW needs to be strengthened to ensure proper use of the national budget, prevent wastage of available resources, and maintain proper standards of healthcare. WHO 2000 report has revealed that wastage of health resources in a country can mount up to 20-40% which,⁴⁶ if prevented, can be directed towards fostering the targeted UHC activities. The government should also consider the separation of their healthcare purchaser and provider territory from a single point (i.e. MoHFW) to enhance accountability and efficiency just as Thailand did.⁴⁵

The second major barrier towards UHC in Bangladesh is their regressive health financing structure, which is mainly supported through OOPE. This privatization of health financing is responsible for increasing inequity in the provision and access of healthcare between their rich and poor populations. Since 31.5% of the Bangladeshi population live below the poverty line, this dependence on OOPE makes them highly vulnerable to financial hardship and prevents millions of poor people from seeking necessary healthcare despite the need.⁶ To prevent the incidences of impoverishment associated with healthcare costs, the government needs to increase their national health budget and decrease the percentage of OOPE below 15-20% of the total health expenditures.⁴⁶ The government's plan to launch a single pool of universal 'Social Health Protection Scheme' (SHPS) through the HCFS has been optimistic, but not without practical concerns regarding its structure and implementation. In order to successfully advance towards UHC in Bangladesh, the SHPS should be implemented in a way that provides room for redistribution of funds, risk pooling, and cross-subsidization between different socio-economic groups. However, the approach of making the scheme voluntary for the larger informal sector of the country has put the effective expansion of coverage among the rural and poor households in doubt. The distribution of formal and informal sector households in the country is disproportionate. Hence, failing to coordinate between the two separate parts (i.e., for formal and informal sectors) of the scheme will make it difficult to redistribute funds between these two regimes, and risk pooling will not be possible to the necessary extent. Additionally, to pay just for the premium of the SSK part of the SHPS scheme in all 427 Upazilas of Bangladesh, grossly US\$133.4 million is required each year. But the government has not been able to allocate sufficient revenues to cover this cost so far; therefore, additional sources of funding need to be generated in order to expand and sustain the entire scheme. Innovative and targeted mechanisms to generate revenues for the national health budget need to be designed to cover this deficit. Bangladesh can learn from the example of France which recovered from their health budget deficit by setting national spending targets, reforming provider payment mechanisms, and improving health

insurance related regulatory reforms.⁸ Finally, a comprehensive legal framework along with a robust monitoring and accountability mechanism needs to be established for the successful implementation and sustenance of SHPS.³⁹ Finally, the health workforce challenges need to be tackled through building a futuristic and organized health workforce development and management strategy. Careful policy making, planning, and implementation are required at the national level to address the shortage and skill-mix imbalance issues in the health workforce. Producing more doctors, nurses and other formally qualified cadre healthcare staff is a lengthy process and it could be decades before the proper balance in the workforce can be achieved. Meanwhile, the government can consider the option of 'task-shifting' to improve population and service coverage, which can be done by assigning the community health workers (CHWs) in rural and underserved areas to provide basic healthcare services.¹⁴ The Ethiopian government created a shorter-length education curriculum for their 'Health Extension Workers' so that they can train and deploy them rapidly in their rural and underserved areas. This way they have been able to deploy more than 35000 health workers in their community and efficiently tackle the shortage of HRH in their country.⁴⁷ Bangladesh needs to learn from their success, and invest more in developing a broader pool of CHWs to tackle the HCP shortage issues. Data has also shown that compared to the unqualified informal HCPs currently practicing in the country, the skills and ability of the trained CHWs are more reliable and cost-effective in providing basic care, health education and referral guidance.⁴⁸ The skill-mix imbalance issues in the health sector have developed due to the country's lack of emphasis on producing a well-balanced health workforce since their early development days. Particularly, the need for the production of nurses and other support staff was ignored in their national health policies and plans. Hence, urgent attention needs to be paid to restore the standard ratio of doctors and other essential healthcare staff through strategic planning and policy-making. There are several factors that discourage people to pursue nursing and other hospital support staff professions, such as low salary, lack of respect and social standing compared to the doctors, poor working environment, long working hours, socio-cultural prejudice, and lack of rewards or recognition for their work.⁶ Therefore, MoHFW needs to take robust initiatives to publicly promote the significance of their profession and recognize the contribution of nurses and other cadres of health staff. The traditional models of education and training programs for nurses, medical technologists, and other healthcare staff also need to be reformed following international standards to increase the inclusivity and quality of the programs. Additionally, the government should focus on establishing lucrative incentive models for the nurses, paramedics, and other hospital staff to motivate them to join the profession. Finally, as evident from the examples of Brazil and Turkey, a combination of strategies can be adopted to resolve the issue of the geographical maldistribution of HCPs in Bangladesh. Such strategies include- a) providing monetary and non-monetary incentives for working in rural areas, b) recruiting students from underserved areas through scholarships and quota methods, c) rotating placement of HCPs between hospitals and primary care sites, and d) establishing innovative and more flexible career paths within the public services.^{8, 49}

5. Conclusion

It goes without saying that for a poverty-ridden and overpopulated country like Bangladesh, it is difficult to arrange all the resources required to build a sustainable and well-functioning health system overnight. But there are numerous examples of countries that have developed a health system capable of positively advancing toward UHC despite their delicate economic circumstances. The approaches of such countries have been successful because of their government's strong commitment towards improving their socio-political environment, and enhancing their population and service coverage by maximizing the utilization of available resources. Bangladesh needs to learn from their actions and interventions to achieve similar results. Towards that goal, it is imperative to systematically address the identified challenges associated with all three of the above-discussed health system building blocks. Hence, it is of utmost

importance that Bangladesh pays special attention towards establishing a robust, efficient and transparent administrative system of healthcare service provision by employing good governance and leadership practices within their health sector. In addition, well-designed, thorough, and sustainable measures need to be taken in order to effectively resolve their existing health workforce and health financing related challenges to help building an effectively functioning health system capable of achieving UHC in the country.

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